

Additional file III Percentage of the population using substances (ATC level 5) according to polypharmacy status

Substances		All subjects		Polypharmacy <10 substances		Excessive polypharmacy ≥10 substances	
		n	(%)	n	(%)	n	(%)
B01AC06	acetylsalicylic acid ³	1662	42.6	665	40.5	997	44.1
C10AA01	simvastatin	1597	40.9	650	39.5	947	41.9
C03AA03	hydrochlorothiazide	1243	31.8	514	31.3	729	32.3
C07AB07	bisoprolol ²	1199	30.7	480	29.2	719	31.8
A02BC02	pantoprazole ¹	1125	28.8	390	23.7	735	32.5
C08CA01	amlodipine ²	1096	28.1	451	27.4	645	28.5
C09AA05	ramipril	1089	27.9	500	30.4	589	26.1
A11CC05	coleciferol	1048	8	331	20.1	717	31.7
H03AA01	levothyroxine sodium	931	23.8	338	20.6	593	26.2
C03CA04	torasemide	905	23.2	295	17.9	610	27.0

1= potentially inappropriate medication according to EU(7)-PIM list

2= recommended alternative drug according to EU(7)-PIM list

3= recommended alternative drug (<325 mg) according to EU(7)-PIM list